

ARCTIC PASSION

Deliverable 2.7

Final report on number of long-term
preserved datasets (T2.6)

Version 1

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Work package

2 – BRINGING THE ARCTIC DATA SYSTEM TO ACTION

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1. Long-term preserved datasets related to Arctic PASSION

The key motivation of the Arctic PASSION project is to contribute to the co-creation and implementation of a coherent, integrated Arctic observing system. It aims to overcome known flaws in the present observing system by refining its operability, improving and extending pan-Arctic scientific and community-based monitoring and the integration with Indigenous and Local knowledge. It also aims at streamlining the access and interoperability of Arctic Data systems and services and contribute to ensuring the economic viability and sustainability of the observing system. As part of the H2020's Open Research Data Pilot¹, the Data Management Plan for the Arctic PASSION project has been designed to provide the consortium partners with a state-of-the-art data handling workflow that adheres to the FAIR data principles (ensuring that data are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable). All datasets generated or mobilised during the course of the project have been curated and archived by expert data editors in trusted FAIR repositories, improving the long-term preservation and integration of Arctic data and information. Specifically, all processed datasets have been enriched with standardised discovery and use metadata to simplify the reuse of data across providers, standardised web services, applications, protocols or data portals. These represent essential optimisation steps along the data value chain, supporting the process of making data machine-actionable and fit for in order to feed it into decision support systems and inform policy. This benefits not only Arctic communities, but also European and global communities.

To date, a total of 150 Arctic PASSION-related datasets, ranging from atmospheric to ice and oceanographic measurements, have been curated and successfully archived. Of these, 129 datasets (Table 1) have already been published in five trusted data repositories: PANGAEA – Data Publisher for Earth & Environmental Science² (119 records), Zenodo³ (four records), the Norwegian Polar Institute⁴ (three records), the Norwegian Meteorological Institute⁵ (two records), the Italian Arctic Data Center⁶ (one record). These include priority datasets fuelling the Arctic PASSION Pilot Services, such Alex⁷ (Nitze et al. 2024, 2025) and AURORAE⁸ (Cuzzucoli et al. 2025). An additional 21 Arctic PASSION-related datasets are currently pending final publication (Table 2). These datasets include measurements from various sea ice mass balance buoys as well as from automatic weather stations and are now in the final processing step before receiving a permanent DOI. the World Meteorological Organization's (WMO) Global Telecommunication System (GTS) and associated with the Arctic PASSION project are still pending publication following GTS conversion. At the time this report was concluded, the CORDIS EU research results project website for Arctic PASSION still displayed an incomplete list of all project-related data publications compiled via the OpenAIRE service (three records listed). However, the authors of this report have compiled a complete list of all published Arctic PASSION datasets, which are currently pending processing and curation by OpenAIRE services for subsequent final linkage and display in CORDIS.

¹ https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-data-mgt_en.pdf

² <https://pangaea.de>

³ <https://zenodo.org/>

⁴ <https://data.npolar.no/dataset>

⁵ <https://adc.met.no/>

⁶ <https://metadata.iadc.cnr.it/>

⁷ <https://alex.awi.de/>

⁸ <https://arcticaurorae.eu/>

2. Catalogues of long-term preserved Arctic PASSION data records:

Table 1. Published datasets, and Table 2. Datasets pending final publication

Table 1. Full list of Arctic PASSION datasets published at the time of report completion. All datasets have been generated by Arctic PASSION project partners and/or with support of H2020 EC funding for Arctic PASSION. Data publications are sorted in alphabetical order (leading author first name). List of Data Repositories: PANGAEA – Data Publisher for Earth & Environmental Science, Norwegian Meteorological Institute, Norwegian Polar Institute, Zenodo.

#	Full Data Citation	Data Repository
1	Berge, J., Anderson, P., Kupiszewski, P., Granskog, M., Bratrein, M., Divine, D., De La Torre, P., Geoffroy, M., Zolich, A., & Kopec, T. (2025). Data from drifting, autonomous ice-tethered observatories deployed in June 2022 at 89.82N, 26.28W [Data set]. Norwegian Meteorological Institute. https://doi.org/10.21343/WJ48-Y250	Norwegian Meteorological Institute
2	Bertosio, C., Provost C., Sennéchaël N., & Koenig Z. (2022). Arctic Makarov Basin: IAOOS14, IAOOS15 and IAOOS25 ocean CTD-DO profiles in 2015 and 2017 [Data set]. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.17882/83520	Zenodo
3	Cuzzucoli, A., Crotti, I., Dobicic, S., & Pasini, A. (2025). 48-hour (0-24h and 25-48h) PM10 Concentrations Forecast with the AdaptedCrossformer model at European Environmental Agency (EEA) Monitoring Stations (2024) [Data set]. Norwegian Meteorological Institute. https://doi.org/10.21343/969W-Z875	Norwegian Meteorological Institute
4	Dodd, P., Sundfjord, A., & Foss, Ø. (2024a). Amundsen-22 mooring, Amundsen Basin of the Arctic Ocean (2022-2024): Ocean temperature, salinity, pressure, and currents [Data set]. Norwegian Polar Institute. https://doi.org/10.21334/NPOLAR.2024.92445174	Norwegian Polar Institute
5	Dodd, P., Sundfjord, A., & Foss, Ø. (2024b). Nansen-22 mooring, Nansen Basin of the Arctic Ocean (2022-2024): Ocean temperature, salinity, pressure, and currents [Data set]. Norwegian Polar Institute. https://doi.org/10.21334/NPOLAR.2024.67FFB476	Norwegian Polar Institute
6	Dybkjær, G., Suhr, M. B., Gierisch, A. M. U., Kreiner, M. B., Ribergaard, M. H., Wulf, T., & Singha, S. (2025). Arctic PASSION - High Resolution Synthetic Aperture Radar based Risk Index Outcome (AP-RIO) [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.975054	PANGAEA

7	Dybkjær, G., Suhr, M. B., Jensen, A. E. T., & Singha, S. (2025). Arctic PASSION - Polar Monthly Mean Ice Surface Temperature (AP-MMIST) for the time period 1982 to 2024 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.975011	PANGAEA
8	Flores, H., Castellani, G., Wilkinson, J., Valcic, L., Hoppmann, M., Veyssire, G., Karcher, M. J., Nicolaus, M., & Stroeve, J. C. (2023). Hydroacoustic backscatter recorded by buoy 2020AZFP1 in the central Arctic Ocean during Sep 2020—May 2021 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.954939	PANGAEA
9	Granskog, M.A. (2022). Raw data from thermistor string ice mass balance buoy 2021M31 (0.1.0) [Data set]. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.21334/npolar.2022.1037bd1e	Zenodo
10	Hoppmann, M., & Nicolaus, M. (2024a). Snow height on sea ice and sea ice drift from autonomous measurements from buoy 2023S100, deployed during expedition PS138 (ArcWatch-1) [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973277	PANGAEA
11	Hoppmann, M., & Nicolaus, M. (2024b). Snow height on sea ice and sea ice drift from autonomous measurements from buoy 2023S102, deployed during expedition PS138 (ArcWatch-1) [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973281	PANGAEA
12	Hoppmann, M., & Nicolaus, M. (2024c). Snow height on sea ice and sea ice drift from autonomous measurements from buoy 2023S103, deployed during expedition PS138 (ArcWatch-1) [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973291	PANGAEA
13	Hoppmann, M., Scholz, D., & Nicolaus, M. (2024a). Snow height on sea ice and sea ice drift from autonomous measurements from buoy 2023S101, deployed during expedition PS138 (ArcWatch-1) [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973279	PANGAEA
14	Hoppmann, M., Scholz, D., & Nicolaus, M. (2024b). Snow height on sea ice and sea ice drift from autonomous measurements from buoy 2023S124, deployed during expedition PS138 (ArcWatch-1) [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973301	PANGAEA
15	Hoppmann, M., von Appen, W.-J., Allerholt, J., Barz, J., Bienhold, C., Dettling, N., Elliott, F., Engicht, C., Fer, I., Graupner, R., Iversen, M. H., Knppel, N., Lochthofen, N., McPherson, R., Metfies, K., Monsees, M., Nthig, E.-M., Oldenburg, E., Popa, O., ... Kanzow, T. (2024a). Raw physical oceanography, bio-optical and biogeochemical data from mooring Y4-1 on the Yermak Plateau, Arctic Ocean, July 2022 – June 2023 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.974316	PANGAEA

16	Hoppmann, M., von Appen, W.-J., Allerholt, J., Boebel, O., Dettling, N., Elliott, F., Engicht, C., Fer, I., Graupner, R., Lochthofen, N., McPherson, R., Meyer-Kaiser, K., Monsees, M., Reifenberg, S. F., Spiesecke, S., Thomisch, K., Schlindwein, V., & Kanzow, T. (2024b). Raw physical oceanography and ocean current velocity data from mooring Y5-1 on the Yermak Plateau, Arctic Ocean, July 2022 – June 2023 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.974317	PANGAEA
17	Hoppmann, M., von Appen, W.-J., Allerholt, J., Boebel, O., Dettling, N., Elliott, F., Engicht, C., Fer, I., Graupner, R., Lochthofen, N., McPherson, R., Monsees, M., Reifenberg, S. F., Schlindwein, V., Spiesecke, S., Thomisch, K., & Kanzow, T. (2024c). Raw physical oceanography and profiling winch data from mooring Y2-1 on the Yermak Plateau, Arctic Ocean, July 2022 – June 2023 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.974312	PANGAEA
18	Hoppmann, M., von Appen, W.-J., Allerholt, J., Dettling, N., Elliott, F., Engicht, C., Fer, I., Graupner, R., Lochthofen, N., McPherson, R., Meyer-Kaiser, K., Monsees, M., Reifenberg, S. F., Schlindwein, V., & Kanzow, T. (2024). Raw physical oceanography and ocean current velocity data from mooring Y1-1 on the Yermak Plateau, Arctic Ocean, July 2022 – June 2023 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.974309	PANGAEA
19	Hoppmann, M., von Appen, W.-J., Allerholt, J., Dettling, N., Elliott, F., Engicht, C., Fer, I., Graupner, R., Lochthofen, N., McPherson, R., Monsees, M., Reifenberg, S. F., Schlindwein, V., & Kanzow, T. (2024). Raw physical oceanography and ocean current velocity data from mooring Y3-1 on the Yermak Plateau, Arctic Ocean, July 2022 – June 2023 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.974314	PANGAEA
20	Ignezi, A., & Bamber, J. L. (2024). Pan-Arctic land-ice and tundra meltwater discharge database from 1950 to 2021 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.967544	PANGAEA
21	Li, T., Heidler, K., Mou, L., Ignézi, Á., Zhu, X. X., & Bamber, J. (2023). Calving Front Dataset for Marine-Terminating Glaciers in Svalbard 1985-2023 [Data set]. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.10407266	Zenodo
22	Nicolaus, M., & von Albedyll, L. (2024a). Snow height on sea ice and sea ice drift from autonomous measurements from buoy 2023S126, deployed during Charcot expedition 2023 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973302	PANGAEA
23	Nicolaus, M., & von Albedyll, L. (2024b). Snow height on sea ice and sea ice drift from autonomous measurements from buoy 2023S128, deployed during Charcot expedition 2023 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973303	PANGAEA

24	Nikolopoulos, A., Renner, A. H. H., Dodd, P. A., Assmy, P., Chierici, M., Fransson, A., Hallanger, I., Granskog, M. A., Lenss, M. A., Sortland, J. M. S., Wold, A., Steen, H., Nikolopoulos, A., & Dodd, P. A. (2023). CTD profiles from NPI cruise AO-I-2023 to the Fram Strait in June 2023, including core parameters measured from Niskin bottle samples. [Data set]. Norwegian Polar Institute. https://doi.org/10.21334/NPOLAR.2023.9605165A	Norwegian Polar Institute
25	Nitze, I., Lübker, T., & Grosse, G. (2024). Pan-Arctic Visualization of Landscape Change (2003-2022), Arctic PASSION Permafrost Service [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.964814	PANGAEA
26	Nitze, I., Lübker, T., Pohlabein, S., & Grosse, G. (2025). Pan-Arctic Visualization of Landscape Change (2005-2024), Arctic PASSION Permafrost Service [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.983891	PANGAEA
27	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025a). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2012T1 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973328	PANGAEA
28	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025b). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2012T4 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973325	PANGAEA
29	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025c). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2012T30 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973326	PANGAEA
30	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025d). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2012T31 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973324	PANGAEA
31	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025e). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2012T32 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973323	PANGAEA
32	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025f). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2013T2 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973330	PANGAEA
33	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025g). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2014T3 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973337	PANGAEA

34	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025h). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2014T5 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973321	PANGAEA
35	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025i). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2014T8 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973322	PANGAEA
36	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025j). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2014T9 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973315	PANGAEA
37	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025k). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2014T11 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973316	PANGAEA
38	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025l). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2014T13 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973317	PANGAEA
39	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025m). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2014T14 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973320	PANGAEA
40	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025n). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2014T16 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973314	PANGAEA
41	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025o). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2014T17 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973319	PANGAEA
42	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025p). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2014T33 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973318	PANGAEA
43	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025q). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2014T34 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973312	PANGAEA
44	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025r). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2015T19 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973311	PANGAEA

45	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025s). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2015T20 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973313	PANGAEA
46	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025t). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2015T22 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973310	PANGAEA
47	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025u). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2015T23 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973309	PANGAEA
48	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025v). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2015T24 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973308	PANGAEA
49	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025w). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2015T25 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973402	PANGAEA
50	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025x). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2015T26 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973400	PANGAEA
51	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025y). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2015T27 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973403	PANGAEA
52	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025z). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2015T28 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973399	PANGAEA
53	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025aa). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2016T21 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973401	PANGAEA
54	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025ab). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2016T36 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973397	PANGAEA
55	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025ac). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2016T37 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973396	PANGAEA

56	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025ad). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2016T39 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973394	PANGAEA
57	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025ae). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2016T41 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973392	PANGAEA
58	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025af). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2016T42 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973398	PANGAEA
59	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025ag). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2016T43 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973393	PANGAEA
60	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025ah). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2016T44 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973395	PANGAEA
61	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025ai). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2017T45 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973383	PANGAEA
62	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025aj). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2018T7 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973391	PANGAEA
63	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025ak). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2018T35 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973389	PANGAEA
64	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025al). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2018T46 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973388	PANGAEA
65	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025am). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2018T49 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973384	PANGAEA
66	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025an). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2018T50 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973385	PANGAEA

67	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025ao). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2018T51 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973390	PANGAEA
68	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025ap). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2018T52 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973382	PANGAEA
69	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025aq). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2018T53 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973375	PANGAEA
70	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025ar). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2018T54 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973379	PANGAEA
71	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025as). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2018T55 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973374	PANGAEA
72	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025at). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2019T56 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973380	PANGAEA
73	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025au). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2019T57 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973373	PANGAEA
74	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025av). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2019T58 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973386	PANGAEA
75	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025aw). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2019T59 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973377	PANGAEA
76	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025ax). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2019T62 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973387	PANGAEA
77	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025ay). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2019T63 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973372	PANGAEA

78	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025az). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2019T64 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973376	PANGAEA
79	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025ba). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2019T65 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973371	PANGAEA
80	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025bb). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2019T66 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973378	PANGAEA
81	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025bc). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2019T67 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973370	PANGAEA
82	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025bd). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2019T68 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973381	PANGAEA
83	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025be). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2019T69 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973369	PANGAEA
84	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025bf). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2019T70 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973368	PANGAEA
85	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025bg). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2019T71 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973367	PANGAEA
86	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025bh). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2019T72 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973366	PANGAEA
87	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025bi). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2020T60 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973363	PANGAEA
88	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025bj). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2020T61 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973362	PANGAEA

89	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025bk). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2020T73 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973364	PANGAEA
90	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025bl). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2020T74 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973361	PANGAEA
91	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025bm). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2020T75 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973365	PANGAEA
92	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025bn). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2020T76 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973360	PANGAEA
93	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025bo). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2020T77 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973357	PANGAEA
94	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025bp). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2020T78 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973358	PANGAEA
95	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025bq). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2020T79 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973350	PANGAEA
96	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025br). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2020T81 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973355	PANGAEA
97	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025bs). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2020T84 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973353	PANGAEA
98	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025bt). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2020T85 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973356	PANGAEA
99	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025bu). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2021T86 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973349	PANGAEA

100	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025bv). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2021T87 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973351	PANGAEA
101	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025bw). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2022T88 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973352	PANGAEA
102	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025bx). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2022T91 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973347	PANGAEA
103	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025by). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2022T92 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973354	PANGAEA
104	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025bz). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2022T93 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973342	PANGAEA
105	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025ca). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2022T94 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973344	PANGAEA
106	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025cb). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2022T95 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973359	PANGAEA
107	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025cc). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2022T96 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973348	PANGAEA
108	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025cd). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2022T97 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973346	PANGAEA
109	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025ce). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2022T98 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973339	PANGAEA
110	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025cf). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2023T89 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973341	PANGAEA

111	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025cg). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2023T99 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973340	PANGAEA
112	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025ch). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2023T100 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973345	PANGAEA
113	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025ci). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2023T102 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973338	PANGAEA
114	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025cj). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2023T104 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973343	PANGAEA
115	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025ck). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2023T105 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973334	PANGAEA
116	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025cl). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2023T106 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973329	PANGAEA
117	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025cm). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2023T107 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973336	PANGAEA
118	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025cn). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2023T109 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973327	PANGAEA
119	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025co). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2023T110 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973331	PANGAEA
120	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025cp). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2023T111 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973332	PANGAEA
121	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025cq). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2023T112 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973335	PANGAEA

122	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025cr). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoy 2023T114 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973333	PANGAEA
123	Preußer, A., Nicolaus, M., & Hoppmann, M. (2025cs). Snow depth, sea ice thickness and interface temperatures derived from measurements of SIMBA buoys deployed in the Arctic Ocean and Southern Ocean between 2012 and 2023 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.973193	PANGAEA
124	Reifenberg, S. F., von Appen, W.-J., Hoppmann, M., & McPherson, R. (2025). Physical oceanography and current meter data from mooring Y5-1 on the Yermak Plateau, Arctic Ocean, July 2022 – June 2023 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.984856	PANGAEA
125	Reifenberg, S. F., von Appen, W.-J., McPherson, R., & Hoppmann, M. (2025a). Physical oceanography and current meter data from mooring Y1-1 on the Yermak Plateau, Arctic Ocean, July 2022 – June 2023 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.984857	PANGAEA
126	Reifenberg, S. F., von Appen, W.-J., McPherson, R., & Hoppmann, M. (2025b). Physical oceanography and current meter data from mooring Y4-1 on the Yermak Plateau, Arctic Ocean, July 2022 – June 2023 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.984782	PANGAEA
127	Reifenberg, S. F., von Appen, W.-J., McPherson, R., & Hoppmann, M. (2025c). Physical oceanography data from mooring Y2-1 on the Yermak Plateau, Arctic Ocean, July 2022 – June 2023 [Data set]. PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.984769	PANGAEA
128	Tu'dese'cho Wholistic Indigenous Leadership Development, & Snowchange Cooperative. (2025). Tahltan Climate Events Database [Data set]. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14761706	Zenodo
129	Viola, A. P., Mazzola, M., & Vitale, V. (2021). Climate Change Tower Radiation Data (No. https://metadata.iadc.cnr.it/geonetwork/srv/api/records/e4872959-4cf2-48df-8195-e8065411be49) [Data set]. Italian Arctic Data Center.	Italian Arctic Data Center

Table 2. Full list of Arctic PASSION data sets successfully archived and pending final publication at the time of report completion. All data sets have been generated by Arctic PASSION project partners and/or with support of H2020 EC funding for Arctic PASSION. Data publications are sorted in alphabetical order (leading author first name). Data Repository: PANGAEA – Data Publisher for Earth & Environmental Science

#	Full Data Citation	Data Repository
1	Granskog, Mats A (publication year): Auxiliary data from SIMBA-type sea ice mass balance buoy 2022T95 [Data set]. PANGAEA, https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.968032	PANGAEA
2	Granskog, Mats A (publication year): Auxiliary data from SIMBA-type sea ice mass balance buoy 2022T97 [Data set]. PANGAEA, https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.968034	PANGAEA
3	Granskog, Mats A (publication year): Heating induced temperature difference measurements from SIMBA-type sea ice mass balance buoy 2022T95: 30 s after the heating cycle [Data set]. PANGAEA, https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.968364	PANGAEA
4	Granskog, Mats A (publication year): Heating induced temperature difference measurements from SIMBA-type sea ice mass balance buoy 2022T95: 120 s after the heating cycle [Data set]. PANGAEA, https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.968436	PANGAEA
5	Granskog, Mats A (publication year): Heating induced temperature difference measurements from SIMBA-type sea ice mass balance buoy 2022T97: 30 s after the heating cycle [Data set]. PANGAEA, https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.968366	PANGAEA
6	Granskog, Mats A (publication year): Heating induced temperature difference measurements from SIMBA-type sea ice mass balance buoy 2022T97: 120 s after the heating cycle [Data set]. PANGAEA, https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.968452	PANGAEA
7	Granskog, Mats A (publication year): Temperature measurements from SIMBA-type sea ice mass balance buoy 2022T95 [Data set]. PANGAEA, https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.968176	PANGAEA
8	Granskog, Mats A (publication year): Temperature measurements from SIMBA-type sea ice mass balance buoy 2022T97 [Data set]. PANGAEA, https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.968177	PANGAEA

9	Nicolaus, Marcel; Graupner, Steffen; Hoppmann, Mario (publication year): Auxiliary data from SIMBA-type sea ice mass balance buoy 2022T94 [Data set]. PANGAEA, https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.968030	PANGAEA
10	Nicolaus, Marcel; Graupner, Steffen; Hoppmann, Mario (publication year): Auxiliary data from SIMBA-type sea ice mass balance buoy 2022T96 [Data set]. PANGAEA, https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.968033	PANGAEA
11	Nicolaus, Marcel; Graupner, Steffen; Hoppmann, Mario (publication year): Auxiliary data from SIMBA-type sea ice mass balance buoy 2022T98 [Data set]. PANGAEA, https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.968037	PANGAEA
12	Nicolaus, Marcel; Graupner, Steffen; Hoppmann, Mario (publication year): Heating induced temperature difference measurements from SIMBA-type sea ice mass balance buoy 2022T94: 30 s after the heating cycle [Data set]. PANGAEA, https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.968363	PANGAEA
13	Nicolaus, Marcel; Graupner, Steffen; Hoppmann, Mario (publication year): Heating induced temperature difference measurements from SIMBA-type sea ice mass balance buoy 2022T94: 120 s after the heating cycle [Data set]. PANGAEA, https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.968431	PANGAEA
14	Nicolaus, Marcel; Graupner, Steffen; Hoppmann, Mario (publication year): Heating induced temperature difference measurements from SIMBA-type sea ice mass balance buoy 2022T96: 30 s after the heating cycle [Data set]. PANGAEA, https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.968362	PANGAEA
15	Nicolaus, Marcel; Graupner, Steffen; Hoppmann, Mario (publication year): Heating induced temperature difference measurements from SIMBA-type sea ice mass balance buoy 2022T96: 120 s after the heating cycle [Data set]. PANGAEA, https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.968446	PANGAEA
16	Nicolaus, Marcel; Graupner, Steffen; Hoppmann, Mario (publication year): Heating induced temperature difference measurements from SIMBA-type sea ice mass balance buoy 2022T98: 30 s after the heating cycle [Data set]. PANGAEA, https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.968365	PANGAEA
17	Nicolaus, Marcel; Graupner, Steffen; Hoppmann, Mario (publication year): Heating induced temperature difference measurements from SIMBA-type sea ice mass balance buoy 2022T98: 120 s after the heating cycle [Data set]. PANGAEA, https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.968455	PANGAEA

18	Nicolaus, Marcel; Graupner, Steffen; Hoppmann, Mario (publication year): Temperature measurements from SIMBA-type sea ice mass balance buoy 2022T94 [Data set]. PANGAEA, https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.968184	PANGAEA
19	Nicolaus, Marcel; Graupner, Steffen; Hoppmann, Mario (publication year): Temperature measurements from SIMBA-type sea ice mass balance buoy 2022T96 [Data set]. PANGAEA, https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.968173	PANGAEA
20	Nicolaus, Marcel; Graupner, Steffen; Hoppmann, Mario (publication year): Temperature measurements from SIMBA-type sea ice mass balance buoy 2022T98 [Data set]. PANGAEA, https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.968178	PANGAEA
21	Suhr, Magnus Barfod; Dybkjær, Gorm; Jensen, André Emil Toft; Singha, Suman; Gacitua, Guisella; Jepsen, Nis; Hayward, Alexander; Olsen, Ida; Rapp, Dina (publication year): Danish Meteorological Institute Qaanaaq Winter Observatory, Automatic Weather Station measuring temperatures, radiation, and winds (2015-2023) [Data set]. PANGAEA, https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.986656	PANGAEA

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